

of the furfural group in chelation. It may be concluded therefore, that the ligand in complexes (i) and (ii) are tridentate while in the rest of the complexes the ligands are bidentate. Several new bands in the narrow range of $550\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{Cl})$ ⁹ further confirm the probable involvement of the above groups in chelation. In case of complex (iii) the presence of water molecules in coordination sphere was further checked by thermogravimetric analysis. Since no loss of weight of the complex was observed below 110° , we infer that the water is coordinated. In the case complex (ii), however, TGA indicated the presence of water as water of crystallisation.

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Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Magnesium Tetrabromo Oxinate with Some Mono- and Bidentate Ligands

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As a part of our previous work¹ on mixed ligand complexes of magnesium oxinate, we are reporting here the synthesis of some mixed ligand complexes of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate with mono- and bi-dentate ligands.

Experimental

Our usual method of preparation was to take ethanolic solution of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate (corresponding magnesium oxinate was virtually insoluble) and add to it the ethanolic solution of the ligand in slight excess. The mixture was heated on hot plate and stirred for 8 to 10 hr after which it was allowed to cool in a refrigerator. On addition of ether to this cooled solution, the adducts separated out which were filtered, washed with acetone and dried at 90° .

Results and Discussion

The adducts of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate, which are generally yellow in colour, are stable when stored under dry conditions but slowly absorb moisture when exposed to air. These complexes are soluble in polar solvents but insoluble in non-polar solvents. The adducts have higher melting points than the stoichiometric mixture of their ingredients; the transition or decomposition temperature of the complexes are much higher than that of the ligands, showing their greater stability. The colour, decomposition or transition temperatures and analytical values of the adducts are given in Table I.

On comparison of the decomposition/transition temperatures of these complexes with those of the complexes formed by anhydrous magnesium oxinate¹, having the common ligands for both, it has been observed that these are more stable and have higher transition/decomposition temperatures. This difference in stability may be accounted for by assuming that presence of bromine in positions 5 and 7 in magnesium tetrabromo oxinate increases the donor property of this ligand. All these complexes are highly soluble in ethanol, whereas the corresponding mixed ligand magnesium oxinate complexes¹ are all insoluble.

An examination of the infrared spectra of the compound formed with water molecules and magnesium tetrabromo oxinate, shows an extra peak at 862 cm^{-1} , which may be of coordinated water². The infrared spectra of pyridine adducts only show some extra peaks due to the presence of pyridine molecule. Of the two N-H stretching vibrations of ethylenediamine, the 3380 cm^{-1} peak remains unaffected, but the 3316 cm^{-1} peak appears at 3250 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity in the complex. In *o*-phenylenediamine complex, a lower shift of 40 cm^{-1} in the 3316 cm^{-1} peak has been observed.

The spectra of the adducts formed with catechol and ethyleneglycol show a number of unexpected features: (a) one of the O-H stretching frequency of catechol is missing and the second O-H stretching frequency is shifted by about 200 cm^{-1} showing association, (b) a new broad band of medium intensity with submaxima at 2750 cm^{-1} and another at 2600 cm^{-1} are seen in the complex, which are absent in the ingredients. These peaks have been assigned to N...H...O bonding in the complex, (c) another broad band at $1950\text{--}1850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is also seen in the complexes, which is assigned to strong hydrogen bonding O...H...O.

The spectra of the complexes formed with anthranilic acid, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, *o*-nitrophenol, salicylaldehyde show strong hydrogen bond bands between $2700\text{--}2650$ and/or $1900\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are missing in the components. In 1-nitroso-2-naphthol complex, the N=O band at 1640 cm^{-1} in the ligand appears at 1620 cm^{-1} in the complex, while for *o*-nitrophenol adduct, the N=O band appears at 1605 cm^{-1} in the complex.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Transition (t) or decom. (d) temperature °C	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
Mg(8HQ) ₂ Br ₄ =L	Yellow	238 d				
L ₂ Py	Dirty white	165 t	41.87 (42.59)	2.67 (2.98)	6.86 (7.08)	3.00 (3.09)
L ₂ H ₂ O	Yellowish green	140 t	31.78 (32.33)	2.23 (2.30)	3.97 (4.19)	3.38 (3.59)
L ₂ en	Yellow	202 t	33.92 (34.68)	2.65 (2.89)	7.89 (8.09)	3.29 (3.46)
L ₂ 1N2N	Light green	255 d	41.38 (41.79)	2.09 (2.23)	5.10 (5.22)	2.78 (2.98)
L ₂ ONP	Yellow	170 t	36.92 (37.40)	2.00 (2.07)	5.32 (5.45)	3.01 (3.11)
L ₂ SalH	Deep yellow	204 d	39.07 (39.84)	2.17 (2.25)	3.57 (3.71)	3.00 (3.18)
L ₂ Catechol	Yellowish green	185 t	38.22 (38.81)	2.28 (2.42)	3.51 (3.77)	3.09 (3.23)
L ₂ gl	Greenish yellow	202 t	33.89 (34.58)	2.38 (2.59)	3.97 (4.03)	3.21 (3.45)
L ₂ <i>o</i> -phen.	Ash	170 t	38.26 (38.91)	2.51 (2.70)	7.32 (7.56)	3.08 (3.24)
L ₂ AnthA	Brown	150 t	38.69 (39.06)	2.18 (2.34)	5.32 (5.46)	2.98 (3.12)

Py=pyridine; en=ethylenediamine; 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; ONP=*o*-nitrophenol; SalH=salicylaldehyde; gl=ethyleneglycol; *o*-phen=*o*-phenylenediamine; AnthA=anthranilic acid.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) Containing N-Allyl Thiourea and Nitrogen Donor Atoms: Penta and Hexa Coordinated

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SEVERAL mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with thiourea, allyl thiourea, diphenyl thiourea, N-methyl thiourea, N,N-dimethyl thiourea etc., have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. It was thought worthwhile to undertake the study of the complexes of cobalt(II) perchlorate with N-allyl thiourea and morpholine and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the direct addition of cobalt(II) perchlorate, N-allyl thiourea and morpholine or 1,10-phenanthroline in 1:2:2 ratio in methanol followed by the addition of ether

and then crystallisation from hot methanol and final drying *in vacuo*.

Elemental analysis (Table I) carried out by standard methods were consistent with the formulations of the compounds. Conductance measurements were carried out in 10⁻³ M acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 with a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined using Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ by Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded by Elico model CD24 spectrophotometer. These data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance values for the compounds, $\Lambda_M = 153$ and 242 mhos cm² mole⁻¹, indicate 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes, respectively. The values have been calculated on the basis of the formula weight. The magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that both the complexes are paramagnetic. For the first compound $\nu(\text{Cl}-\text{O})$ was observed as two sharp bands at 930 and 620 cm⁻¹ indicating that one of the perchlorate groups is coordinated to the metal ion (620 cm⁻¹) while the other is free (ionic) (930 cm⁻¹)⁵⁻⁸. But in case of the second compound, $\nu(\text{Cl}-\text{O})$ was observed as a single band at 1090 cm⁻¹ indicating that both the perchlorate groups are ionic and not coordinated to metal ion.

Comparison of the ir spectrum of the N-allyl thiourea with those of the complexes shows a -ve shift of the order of 200 cm⁻¹ in NH stretching frequency, suggesting coordination through nitrogen⁷. Again, the bands due to thiomide I [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S}) + \nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$] and thiomide II [$\delta(\text{CH}) + \delta(\text{NH}) +$